

Echoes of Defiance in the Poetic Expression of Meena Kandasamy

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Abstract:

Indian woman poets have offered new scope and magnitude to the literature of India. In ancient times structure of society was patriarchal in nature due to patriarchal assumption women writing undervalued. In literature of India, in course of time feminist ideologies began to influence. In 21 century Indian woman poets projecting new standpoint of life. Even though India is linguistically and culturally diverse country, after independence it has continued its mission of national integration. However, the privileged group of society dominate while working class retain its marginalization. Due to the dominance of upper caste marginalize communities come to the periphery. As result of this centre and periphery division marginalized community has to face social exclusion.

In realm of contemporary Indian literature Kandasamy's voice is emerged as powerful assertive voice. She is poet, fiction writer translator and activist, based in Chennai Her poems give new dimensions to Dalit feminism, social justice and political freedom. Her poems are deeply political and person which give voice to lived experience of marginalize section of society who has been pushed to the margin of mainstream discourse They are not limited to Indian literature but represent a new voice of resistance on a global scale. The Present research paper examines selected poems of Meena Kandasamy, particularly from her collections Touch (2006) and Ms. Militancy (2010)

Keywords: Marginalization, Caste, resistance

Introduction

Meena Kandasamy is one of the prominent and rebellious literary voices of the 21st century. Through poetry, prose, and social movements, she has directly challenged caste discrimination, gender violence, and political oppression. Her literary writing especially poetry represents personal and collective pain as a form of resistance. She has made literature not just a space for beauty but a platform for struggle and change. By analysing the selected poems this paper shows that Kandasamy transforms personal and collective pain into rebellion. Her poems are relevant in 21 centuries due to its ability to relate their personal experience with collective struggle. This makes Meena Kandasamy one of the most important voices in 21st-century Indian literature, whose poetry shows the power of resistance. Kandasamy's voice reaches beyond national boundaries provide impetus to global social justice and feminist movements. Her poems reflect a "21st-century vision of resistance which visualizes a future of liberation.

This article will explore the various forms of resistance that emerge from her writing style. It will show how her voice stands within the framework of Dalit feminism and postcolonial literature. There are echoes of rebellion in her words, reminding us that literature in the 21st century is not just an artistic expression but a struggle for political existence and transformation. This article also highlights Meena Kandasamy as an Emerging Voice. Her selected poems such as "Aggression", "Apologies for Living on", "One-Eyed Ekalavya" reflect new forms of, resistance and rebellion.

Analysis of Poems of Meena Kandasamy

Kandasamy in her poetry collection *Touch* (2006) and *Ms Militancy* (2010) expresses her outrage toward unjust treatment meted out to Dalits and the taboos imposed by dominant caste. Being Dalit, she thinks that protest, radical change and uprising are inevitable for the social transformation. For rediscovering her Dalit identity, she attempts to create her own history. She refutes religious history by deconstructing Hindu and Tamil Mythologies. The present research paper aims to analyse outrage and burning indignation towards social injustice particularly the exploitation of Dalits and Dalit woman that revealed in Meena Kandasamy poems.

In her poem entitled "Aggression" she holds the belief that should not remain silent, she tries to influence woman to voice against dominant caste system that has weakened the identity of woman, women should stand up against injustice in the society. The following lines from the poem *Aggression* provides an insight into the essence of defiant nature.

Sometimes,
The outward signals of Inward struggle take colossal forms.
And the revolution happens because our dream explodes most of the time.
Aggression is the best kind of trouble shooting

(Aggression 7-10)

Here poet expresses the strength and power of aggression. It is the answer to every injustice. The poet highlights that in society suppressed emotion will take and get exploded and give birth to revolution. She strongly reiterates that aggression is the best form of troubleshooting. Rebellion, defiance and aggression are tools of empowerment.

In the poem "Apologies for Living on" female identity is redefined by exposing patriarchal structures. Women are vulnerable in male dominated social set up. Here we see explicit reference of gender-based violence and how female body has been objectified. The following lines from the poem "Apologies for living on" reflect impotence of woman who desire to be liberated themselves like birds try to evade by patriarchal restrictions

I was helpless girl
Against brutal world of
bottom patting and breast pinching
I was craving for security
the kind had only known a while

(Touch)

In her poem "One-Eyed" she portrays the continued existence of oppressive structure of caste class race and gender discrimination with Indian society. In this poem little girl for quenching her thirst touches the pot and drank a glass of water. When teacher notice that touch, he slapped the girls for breaking the rules. drinking water is the pot is only meant for upper caste student. She has to lose her one eyes simply for drinking water from the pot. The following lines highlights brutal caste oppression and her defiance

dham sees a world torn in half
he left eyes lit open but light slpped away
the price for a taste of that touchable water
(Ms. Militancy 9-10)

Here loss of eyesight indicates physical loss and social exclusion Dalit student has to suffer at the hands of teacher. These lines exposes the approach of institution like school, healthcare and media

In Ekalavya" Meena kandasamy reinterprets 'Guru Dronacharya and Ekalavya famous story of Mahabharata. Guru Dronacharya was illustrious teacher. Ekalavya was his disciple. He was gifted archer from lower caste. He acquired skill of archery from his guru. He ask Eklavya Guru Dakshina that a teacher owes his teacher upon completion of his training in archery. Dranchaya ask for right thumb, knowing that it will hamper Ekalavya ability to pursue archery. Eklalyn's unwavering dedication to his guru Silenced in the name of loyalty. She highlights he defiance, as She says

"You don't need your right thumb
to pull a trigger or hurt a bomb"
(Touch 7-8)

The above line implies the violent defiance is tool to dismantle entrenched caste hierarchies. she expresses her defiance through poetry to empower the Marginalized.

Conclusion:

A close reading of Meena Kandasamy's poems reveal her defiance against entrenched caste hierarchies. Her poems give new dimensions to Dalit feminism, social justice and political freedom. They are not limited to Indian literature but represent a new voice of resistance on a global scale. Her poems prove that literature is not just a space of beauty but a political struggle for existence and transformation. In these poems, the voice of women is given new strength. She asserts that women are not just sufferers but, fighters.

Her poems illustrate the power of resistance and make literature a tool for social justice and transformation. They stand against caste, patriarchy and oppression and imagine a future of liberation. The defiance seen in her poems is not only individual but also collective. She expresses the pain of the Dalit community, the struggles of women through her poetry. Therefore, her poems acquire special significance in the social and political context. Finally, Meena Kandasamy is one of the important and globally influential voices of resistance in Indian literature of the 21st century.

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